

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17426824

Effect of Class Size on Students' Academic Performance in Social Studies in Junior Secondary Schools in Yobe State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effects of class size on students' academic performance in social studies in JUNIOR secondary schools in Yobe state, Nigeria. The objectives of the research are: effect of class size on students' academic performance in social studies in Junior Secondary Schools in Yobe State and effect of class size on the academic performance male and female students' Junior secondary schools in Yobe State. The expo-facto research design was employed in this study. Data used in the study was obtained from students' performance. The study targeted all the Junior secondary schools in Yobe State. A sample of 449 respondents was used in the study. Simple percentage, mean, standard deviation and t-test statistics were used for analysing the data. The study revealed: there was a significant difference between the mean academic performances of junior secondary school students in social studies in class sizes; there was a significant difference between the mean academic performance of urban and rural students in Junior secondary schools in Social Studies due to class size in Yobe State. The study recommended that: The Government shall as a matter of urgency provide enough classrooms to cater for the teeming students population and/or alternative classrooms should be erected especially in the urban centres where there are large number of enrolments and/or introduce a shift arrangement of students (morning/evening) before the final solution is provided.

Keywords: academic performance, class size, Junior secondary schools

INTRODUCTION

Classroom is a core factor that educational planners take into consideration in the effort to achieve stipulated objectives in the educational system. Research has shown that there is a link between low pupil's performance and increase in the class size. This, without doubt, is due to the apparent effect of overcrowding on effective learning both for the pupil and the teacher. The national Policy on Education (FGN 2004) recommended that the teacher-student ratio for Secondary Schools should be 1:40. In emphasizing the importance of class-size to the learning-teaching process, All Nigerian Conference of Principals of Secondary Schools (ANCOPSS) recommended a maximum of forty students per class for efficient and effective teaching. Adeyemi (2008) in his findings on the influence of class size on the quality of output in secondary schools revealed that schools with an average class size of 35 and below obtained better results in the secondary school certificate examination (SSCE) than schools with more than 35 students per class.

However, with the introduction of Universal Basic Education (JUNIOR) in 2004 to complement the defunct UPE program of 1976, school enrolment increased tremendously. In the words of Nwogu (2006) the explosive increase led to overcrowded classes to the extent that teachers were made to teach between 50-100 students in a class; this led to oversized schools with oversized classes. Classes become too large for a single teacher to handle especially in areas of practical demonstration and individual correction of practical work. In almost all the states of Nigeria the problem of finance has not allowed the provision of more teachers to match the increasing enrolment of students in schools. It is therefore the thrust of this study to find out the effects of class size on the students' academic performance in JUNIOR Secondary Schools in Yobe State.

Oguntoye (2011) in his own study found that class-size had negative coefficient with student's academic performance in examination. Xinyi (2006) informed that students' performance has been a subject of national case and comparative studies among countries since the beginning of the use of educational theory. Aremu (2001) was of the view that academic performance is a fundamental criterion by which all teaching-learning activities are measured, using some standards of excellence and the acquisition of particular grades in examinations which measures candidate's ability, mastery of the content, and skills in applying the knowledge acquired to a particular situation. Fafunwa (2010) postulated that there is a gap in the quality of students that are in crowded classrooms, who use inadequate and absolute equipment, and have disillusioned teachers. According to him, these combined deficiencies perhaps affect student's academic performance. Similarly, Egede (2005) pointed out that an alarming class size of 100 or more students in secondary school leaves the teacher overworked and therefore unable to exercise patience and positive attitude. They are also reluctant to offer extra time to build and help the intellectually ill students.

Onah (2008) aptly notes in this regard that the essence of having a manageable class size is to ensure that the understanding rates of each of the learners, their respective general background are put in to consideration by the teacher in the course of his teaching. Yara (2011) in his study on class size and academic performance of students in mathematics in southern Nigeria found out that the performance of students in large classes was very low (23%) compared to students in smaller classes (64%). Asiyai and Ajudeonu (2010) asserted that academic performance of students depends on the effectiveness of instruction provided by teachers. This they said can only take place in a classroom of manageable size. Osim (2009) found that class size as one of the variables of school quality exert significant influence on teachers' task performance in terms of learning, assessment of students' academic performance and classroom management. Teaching large classes, according to Wosyanju (2005), negatively affects the morale, motivation and self-esteem of teachers. The author further reported that many teachers feel that when teaching large classes, they spend more time in organizing class activities and not enough time on meeting students' need individually. In tracing the causes of poor academic performance among students in secondary schools in Nigeria a number of factors have been identified. These include inadequate teaching staff, non-availability of instructional materials, poor methods of instruction as well as high population and inadequate classrooms. In this case, parents blame government for poor funding of education especially secondary education. They also blame teachers for poor performance of students while on the other teachers blame the government for untimely payment of salaries. Government on its part blames teachers for their ineffectiveness and parents for negligence of their parental responsibilities (Uba, 2009).

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effects of class size on the academic performance of Social Studies Students in Urban and Rural Secondary Schools in Yobe State. The specific objectives are to:

1. Find out the effect of class size on the students' academic performance in social studies in JUNIOR secondary Schools in Yobe State.
2. To ascertain the disparity in the academic performance of JSS Students in social studies urban and rural JUNIOR secondary Schools in Yobe State.

Research Questions

In line with each specific objective, the following research questions are raised:

1. what is the effect of class size on the academic performance JUNIOR secondary school students in social studies in Yobe State?
2. To what extent is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of urban and rural JUNIOR secondary schools' students due to class size in Yobe State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses will be tested in the study:

- i. There is no significant effect of class size on the academic performance of JSS students in Social Studies in Yobe State.
- ii. There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of urban and rural JSS students in Urban and Rural secondary schools in Social Studies due to class size in Yobe State.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Ex-post facto Research Design was employed in conducting the study. The design involves collecting and analysing existing data. The choice of the design is based on the opinion of Neil (2010) who highlighted that ex-post facto study or after-the-fact research is a category of research design in which the investigation starts after the fact has occurred without interference from the researcher, this particular design is chosen on the account of the nature of the study.

A sample size of 449 JUNIOR Secondary School students was based on Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table of sample size determination. One school is to be randomly selected from each of the six randomly selected local governments of Gashua Educational zone of Yobe state making a total number of six schools. Based on this process, the following schools was be selected; Government Day Junior Secondary School Ramat Gashua, Government Day Junior Secondary School Dachia, , Government Day Junior Secondary School Machina, Government Day Junior Secondary School Girgiri Nguru and Government Day Junior Secondary School Lawanti.as shown in Table 2.

Table 1: Distribution of Sample Schools and Students Population

S/N	LGA	Schools	Male	Female	Total
1.	Bade	GDJSS Ramat	49	35	84
2	Jakusko	GDJSS Dachia	49	35	84
3	Karasuwa	GDJSS Gasma	49	27	76
4	Machina	GDJSS Machina	31	19	50
5	Nguru	GDJSS Girgiri	44	30	74
6	Yusufari	GDJSS Lawanti	46	35	81
Total			268	181	449

The instrument used to collect data for this study is the students' academic records (performance scores) of Social Studies for three years obtained from the school academic office (indicated in table two).

Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question and t-test statistics was used to test the Null hypotheses.

RESULTS PRESENTATION ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Respondents Personal Information

A total of 449 respondents were sampled and used as ex-post factor for the research. All the 449 respondents were critically examined for the study. Thus, the analysis was based on 449 respondents.

Table 2: Distribution of Samples by Urbanization

Location	Frequency	Percentage
Urban	207	46.1
Rural	242	53.9
Total	449	100.0

Table 4 shows the distribution of the respondents by location. Out of the total number of students respondents involved in the study, 207 or 46.1% are from urban school while 242or 53.9% are from rural school. In this distribution rural school respondents outnumbered the urban school respondents

Answering of Research Questions

Three research questions that were raised in chapter one guides the study and the results were analysed using statistical mean and standard deviation. They are as follows:

Research Question One: *What is the of class size on the academic performance score JUNIOR students in social studies in Yobe State?*

To answer this research question, the mean score and the standard deviation of subjects from secondary schools were computed. Table 4 presents the mean scores for the two groups

Table 3: Mean Performance score and standard Deviation of students in Junior Secondary Schools

School Type	N	Mean	SD	Mean diff
overcrowded	291	149.25	23.566	-15.841
Non-overcrowded	158	165.09	26.565	

As illustrated in Table 6, subjects in urban schools (291) had mean performance score of 149.25 with a standard deviation of 23.563 while subjects in Rural schools (158) had a mean performance score of 165.09 and a standard deviation of 26.565. The mean difference is 15.841 in favour of Rural schools that are not overcrowded. This means that students in the class sizes had lower mean performance score than their counterparts in the non – congested classrooms. Therefore, the academic performance of Junior secondary school students is affected by the large number of students in the classroom.

Research Question Two: *To what extent is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of urban and rural JSS students’ in JUNIOR secondary schools due to class size in Yobe State?*

To answer this research question, the mean score and the standard deviation of subjects from rural and urban JUNIOR secondary schools were computed. Table 7 presents the mean scores for the two groups.

Table 4: Mean Performance score and standard Deviation of students in Urban schools and Rural schools

Location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Diff
Urban	207	143.91	24.175	-20.240
Rural	242	164.15	25.068	

As indicated in Table 7, subjects in urban schools (207) had mean performance score of 143.91 with a standard deviation of 24.175 while subjects in rural schools (242) had a mean performance scores of 64.49 and a standard deviation of 11.976. The mean difference is 20.240 in favour of rural subjects. This means that subjects in urban schools had lower mean score than their rural counterparts. Therefore, the mean performance score of Junior secondary school students in rural schools is higher than that of their urban counterparts in Yobe state.

Testing of Null Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis One

There is no significant effect of class size on the mean academic performance score of students in JUNIOR secondary schools in Yobe State.

In order to test the hypothesis, the mean performance scores of overcrowded and non – overcrowded were subjected to t-test analyses. Table 9 presents the students t-test for the two groups.

Table 5: Independent Sample t-test Analysis of mean performance scores of students in urban and rural Schools

School Type	N	Mean	t	Df	P value
Class size	291	149.25	-6.274	447	.000
Non- class size	158	165.09			

Table 9 shows that $t(449) = -6.274$, $df = 447$, $p = .001 < 0.05$. This indicates that the probability value (p) is lower than the alpha level of significance ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, since the p value is lower than the alpha level, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference between the effects of class size in on students’ academic performance in JUNIOR secondary Schools Yobe State.

Null Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of urban and rural students in JUNIOR secondary schools due to class size in Yobe State.

In order to test the hypothesis, the mean performance scores of urban students and their rural counterparts in JUNIOR secondary schools were subjected to t-test analyses. Table 10 presents the students t-test for the two groups.

Table 6: Independent samples t-test Analysis of Subjects in Urban and Rural Schools

Location	N	Mean	T	Df	P value
Urban	207	143.91	-8.669	447	.000
Rural	242	164.15			

The in Table 10 illustrates, that $t(449) = -8.669$, $df - 447$, $p = .001$, at 0.05. This indicates that the probability value (p) is lower than the alpha level of significance ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, since the p value is lower than the alpha level, the null hypothesis is here by rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference between the effect of class size in urban and rural Schools on the academic performance of JSS students in Yobe State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study investigated the effects of class sizes on students’ academic performance in Junior secondary schools in Yobe state, Nigeria. From the analysis of the hypotheses one and two the following findings were discussed.

Finding from the analysis of hypotheses one reveals that, there is a significant effect of class size on the mean academic performance score of students in JUNIOR secondary schools in Yobe ($t = -6.274$, $df = 447$, $p = .001 < 0.05$). The students in overcrowded schools (291) had mean performance score of 149.25 with a standard deviation of 23.566 while subjects in rural schools (158) had a mean performance score of 165.09 and a standard deviation of 26.565. This shows that the mean performance scores of non – overcrowded students is higher than that of their overcrowded counterparts. This implies that students who attend secondary school with less population perform better than those who attend schools that have large class size. This finding is expected because overcrowded could not carter individual students needs and hence, lower in the performance while in the non- congested classroom teachers can easily the individual needs of the students since, they are not much which has positive impact on the students. The reverse is the case in rural schools. ($t = -3.537$, $p < 0.05$). This finding confirms Fabunmi, et al (2007) finding that class size is a factor influencing academic performance of students.

Finding from the analysis of hypotheses two reveals that there is a significant difference between the mean performance scores of urban and rural JSS students in Social Studies due to large class size in Yobe State ($t = -8.669$, $df = 447$, $p = .001$, at 0.05). The students in urban schools (207) had mean performance score of 143.91 with a standard deviation of 24.175 while subjects in rural schools (242) had a mean performance score of 64.49 and a standard deviation of 11.976. This shows that the mean performance scores of students in rural school are higher than that of their urban counterparts. This implies that students who attend rural secondary school perform better than those who attend urban schools because of the large class size. This finding could be attributed to the fact that students in urban areas are overcrowded in the class.

This finding corroborates the decisions of parents who send their children to rural schools for better academic performance. The finding of this study contradicts the finding Yusuf and Adigun (2010) who found no significant difference between the academic performance of rural and urban students. ($t_{\text{cal}} = 0.68$, $df = 38$; $t_{\text{crit}} = 1.7$), and of Owoeye and Yara (2011).

CONCLUSION

Emanating from the findings of this study, the following conclusions are drawn:

- i. Junior secondary school student's academic performance in small class size is better than that of their large class counterpart in Yobe State.
- ii. Junior secondary school students' academic performance in rural Schools is better than that of their urban counterpart in Yobe State;

RECOMMENDATIONS

Emanating from the findings of this study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Government as a matter of urgency should provide enough classroom to accommodate the teeming youth for effective academic activities in classroom especially in the urban areas where they are densely populated.
2. An alternative learning space should be provided by the authorities in lieu of the classroom in order to decongest the classes for effective course delivery'
3. Government should pave a way for shift/ splitting of the activities in the urban schools where students are much pending erection of the needed structures.

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